

POLLUTION AND HUMAN HEALTH

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last three decades there has been increasing global concern over the public health impacts attributed to environmental pollution, in particular, the global burden of disease. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that about a quarter of the diseases facing mankind today occur due to prolonged exposure to environmental pollution. Recent reports have shown that approximately around 50,000 people dies daily due to water pollution only.

The main reason behind this rapid increase in pollution is the Human greed of development and industrialization.

Recent reports have shown that with this rapid rate of conservation of natural sources of energy, natural biomass sources would completely vanish from the earth in less than 20years. Clearly, Human Greed has taken over human need of development. In this blind race of industrialization, mankind has forgotten that how much it is affecting our environment and what drastic results would occur if we continue to disrespect the nature. With this rate of pollution, many severe issues such as Global Warming and depletion of ozone layer etc.

In the 8 years that have passed, the political context of environment and health has evolved. As highlighted in EEA's The European Environment— state and outlook 2010 the policy focus is increasingly shifting from single environmental pollution issues towards systemic challenges regarding the maintenance of ecosystem resilience and the delivery of ecosystem services to human society.

Environment and health is not just 'an aspect' of environmental policy, it is at the heart of it. In fact, it is central to Europe's ambition to move towards a Green Economy. With this report, taking stock of the most pertinent environment and health issues, and combining the expertise of our two institutes in environmental reporting and scientific research, we hope to contribute to this goal.

WATER POLLUTION

The water we drink is essential ingredients for our wellbeing and a healthy life. Unfortunately polluted water and air are common throughout the world according to European Public Health Alliance, 2009. The WHO states that one sixth of the world's population, approximately 1.1 billion people do not have access to safe water and 2.4 billion lack basic sanitation. Polluted water consists of sewage water, Industrial discharged effluents, rain water pollution and polluted by agriculture or households cause damage to human health or the environment. This water pollution affects the health and quality of soils and vegetation. Estimation indicates that more than fifty countries of the world with an area of twenty million hectares area are treated with polluted or partially treated polluted water, and this poor quality water causes health hazard and death of human being, aquatic life and different crops. In present scenario due to industrialization and increased population, the

drains of India carry the industrial and municipal effluents that are ultimately carried that polluted water to the canals and rivers. The untreated industrial and municipal wastes have created multiple environmental hazards for mankind, irrigation, drinking and sustenance of aquatic life. This water pollution infected our food in addition to groundwater contamination when used to irrigate crops. Thus essential steps should be taken to control to effects of water pollution throughout the globe in order to bring the water pollution under control.

AIR POLLUTION

Apart from increasing water pollution, one of the major types of pollution which has gained the concerns of authorities all over the world is Air Pollution. The rate at which urban air pollution has grown across India is alarming. Almost all cities are reeling under severe particulate pollution while newer pollutants like oxides of nitrogen and air toxics have begun to add to the public health challenge. Only a few mega cities where action has started show some improvement in air quality but in most cases the particulate levels are still unacceptably high.

Improve air quality monitoring to include more pollutants and more areas in cities to assess the risk of air pollution, make appropriate policies to control it and to create awareness amongst people about hard policy decisions. Ambient air quality standards are constantly evolving to address the emerging health challenges. We need to act fast as the gathering evidence worldwide convinces that India requires a leapfrog agenda to address the public health crisis looming large due to rapidly growing air pollution. India needs strong policy interventions to enable research in the field of air pollution. Health-based criteria should become the basis of air quality regulations. There aren't too many comprehensive and systematic epidemiological studies to examine the magnitude of adverse health impacts due to air pollution in India. The absence of an explicit national policy interlocking health-based criteria with air quality management is largely to be blamed for this lack of initiative. It is extremely important that the government accepts the precautionary principle and integrates health evidences with policymaking.

SOIL POLLUTION

Improper management of solid waste is one of the main causes of environmental pollution. Land pollution is one of the major forms of environmental catastrophe our world is facing today. As Bulgaria and the Slovak Republic, heavy metal industries have produced wastes that are deposited into landfills without special precautions, posits that approximately half of the population lives in the vicinity of waste sites that do not conform to contemporary standards in Romania. Czech Republic's coal and uranium mines have produced serious pollution problems though out the world, and much of the solid industrial waste containing heavy metals is disposed of, without pretreatment, in open dumps. Recent studies have concluded as the worst pollution of Hungary comes from open cast mines, lignite-based power plants, chemical factories, and the aluminum industry. The Silesia district in the south of Poland has severe contamination from mining and industry.

EFFECTS OF DYING ENVIRONMENT ON HUMAN, ANIMALS AND PLANTS

Environment dying is global perilous point which catastrophically affects the humans, animals and plants. Air pollution results are Cancer, neurobehavioral disorders , cardiovascular problems , asthma, headaches and dizziness , irritation of eyes, nose, mouth and throat , reduced lung functioning etc. . Air pollutants can also indirectly affect human health through acid rain, by polluting drinking water and entering the food chain, and through global warming and associated

climate change and sea level rise. Acid rain also destroys fish life in lakes and streams and kill trees, destroy the leaves of plants, unwarranted ultraviolet radiation through the ozone layer eroded by some air pollutants, may cause skin cancer in wildlife and damage to trees and plants, and . Polluted drinking water or water polluted by chemicals produced waterborne diseases like Typhoid, Liver and kidney damage. Loss of wild life is directly related to pollution. For tree and plants water pollution may disrupt photosynthesis in aquatic plants and thus affecting ecosystems that depend on these plants. Soil pollution closely associated to air and water pollution, soil pollution can alter metabolism of plants' metabolism and reduce crop yields and same process with microorganisms, and thus have a negative effect on predator animal class. Small life forms may consume harmful chemicals which may then be passed up the food chain to larger animals; this may lead to increased mortality rates and even animal extinction.

CONCLUSION

Mankind should think what kind of future they are leaving for our next generation. With every little action they take, they might leave better future for the upcoming generations. With the use of natural nonpolluting sources of energy, use of renewable sources of energy such as wind energy, water energy etc., we might save our planet's environment and may be able to create a better and beautiful future for the upcoming generations.